

Better Modelling Improves Non-Animal Chemical Safety Assessment

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Abstract

Computational, or *in silico*, approaches are fundamental in 21st Century toxicology, providing means of estimating hazard and exposure to a particular xenobiotic in a particular use case scenario. Interest in computational toxicology is growing strongly and linked to new technologies in artificial intelligence. Whilst it is attractive to create models rapidly using some of the comprehensive data sets now available, we need to remember concepts of good modelling. Approaches such as the OECD QSAR Principles and ECHA RAAF are well established to promote valid models and acceptable predictions. However, we believe that modellers interested in supporting chemical safety assessment should go further. For instance, problem formulation is well established in safety assessment, but is often lacking in computational modelling. Problem formulation allows for the aim of the model to be stated and for “acceptance” criteria to be established. To support development of high-quality models, data quality should be assessed. The problem formulation exercise should identify whether a “quick and dirty” approach to model development is sufficient, or whether more effort should be placed in quality assessment which is shown to lead to better models. Evaluation of models should be undertaken in the context of demonstrating the “credibility” of the models, i.e. their verification, validation and assessment of uncertainties. Relating to uncertainties, new approaches, based around EFSA guidance have been developed which allow for definition of “tolerable” uncertainty in areas such as read-across. When models are available, they should be FAIR. The “FAIR Lite” principles have recently been proposed which simplify the demonstration and process of FAIRification of *in silico* approaches.

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